

Photonic textiles for biomedical applications

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ABSTRACT

“Smart textiles” encompasses a range of textile materials that react or adapt to physical stimuli (e.g., thermal, electrical, chemical, etc.), and combine both specialty materials and integrated electronics and computing power. They are established as continuous monitoring solutions for the human health, with numerous projects being pursued towards the monitoring of heart rate and respiration, body temperature, movement and muscle activity, among others. In this talk, we will describe the activities of Empa in the field of photonic textiles, a sub-class of "smart textiles" where photonic elements (optical fibers or fluorophores) are integrated into textiles.

KEYWORDS: polymer optical fibers, fluorescent, wound monitoring, textiles, healthcare

INTRODUCTION

“Smart textiles” encompasses a range of textile materials that react or adapt to physical stimuli (e.g., thermal, electrical, etc.), and combine both specialty materials and integrated computing power. “Smart textiles” which contain photonic materials such as optical fibers or fluorescent moieties are also referred to as photonic textiles.

In this talk, we will describe several materials and prototypes developed at Empa in the field of photonic textiles. This includes: a) a photoplethysmography (PPG), to be used in reflection mode for the prevention of decubitus ulcers; b) a respiratory rate sensor based on pressure-sensitive optical fibers; and c) textile chemical sensor based on fluorescence POFs for identification of metabolites in body fluids (e.g., monitoring of wound exudate).

They are intended for the continuous monitoring of elderly people and/or chronic patients, as well as wearable/transdermal delivery devices.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Physical sensors based on photonic textiles

For the development of novel sensors or treatment options in healthcare, photonic textiles can provide valuable options. They have to fulfill various prerequisites for textile production as well as sensor performance. We will report our recent developments of polymer optical fibers (POFs) with exceptional properties and their subsequent integration into textiles for the design of a range of wearable sensors or therapy devices.

Our polymer optical fibers were produced by melt-spinning of thermoplastic polymers. The different types of polymer optical fibers show high flexibility to allow for textile integration while continuously transferring the signal. Among other properties, the fibers' mechanical and optical properties were investigated.

We have realized different types of photonic textiles, with different applications.

a) Heart rate/oxygen saturation[1,2]: flexible, photonic textile based-sensor for the continuous monitoring of the PPG signal for heart rate and blood oxygenation measurements with a lower static coefficient of friction (COF) than conventionally-used bedsheets.

The used bi-component polymer optical fibers (POFs) were melt-spun and continuously embroidered or woven to form sensing structures. The resulting sensor withstands disinfection. Measurement accuracy can be compared to commercial devices.

b) Pressure sensors[3,4]: Mono-component POFs were produced continuously by melt-extrusion or batch-wise by molding. Advantageously for pressure sensing, the unclad fibers are more susceptible to macro-bending. We showed linear responses of change in light intensity to load on the fiber as well as a correlation between production parameters and mechanical properties.

Chemical sensors based on fluorescent POFs

We realized non-invasive lab-on-fiber multi-sensing technologies for monitoring metabolites in wound exudate (e.g., pH, glucose, protease, etc.).[5-7] Firstly, we developed fluorescent-based sensing chemistries for the biomarkers. For instance, we designed molecularly imprinted hydrogels capable of detecting glucose with good sensitivity and selectivity[6]. pH-responsive dye-conjugated polymer was synthesized to ensure efficient fiber functionalization and limit the undesired leakage of the fluorophore[7]. Moreover, gelatin nanoparticles were fabricated to achieve the fluorescent detection of metalloproteinase. We are currently focusing on functionalizing POFs with optimized sensing chemistries to improve the sensitivity and robustness of detection. Such functionalized POFs will then be incorporated into textile patches/garments aiming to

simultaneously detect the targeted biomarkers with spatial resolution. These patches will then be used for an extensive study in patients for monitoring the healing process of acute or chronic wounds.

Figure 1: (a) Example of a photonic textile sensor containing embroidered POFs for measuring oxygen saturation.[1]
(b) Example of a photonic textile sensor containing fluorescent hydrogels for wound monitoring.[5]

CONCLUSIONS

Photonic textiles offer great potential for the health monitoring sector. The potential of POFs is still not fully exploited and their use in smart textiles will increase in the coming years.

Further development of optical sensors for integration into wearable/textile systems as additional diagnostic tools for the personalization of medicine is ongoing. Specially important is the feasibility of early diagnosis via continuous monitoring of risk patients.

Examples of future and ongoing projects on photonic textiles include: wearable luminescent solar concentrators as autonomous energy sources for wearable devices; printing of photodetectors on the POFs for improved multiplexing; development of closed-loop drug delivery systems enabling the controlled release of therapeutics as a function of bio-signals relevant to pathological processes; and the coupling of wearable sensors with human avatars (digital twins) to promote precise and personalized therapy.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work was supported by the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) and Innosuisse BRIDGE Discovery funding opportunity (project number 40B2-0_180983); the Strategic Focal Area “Personalized Health and Related Technologies (PHRT)” of the ETH Domain (grant #2018-532); the Nano-Tera.ch (with the ParaTex and the ParaTex-Gateway projects) with Swiss Confederation financing; and the Swiss Innovation Agency (project number 28744.1 IP-ENG). The students and researchers that worked on the mentioned projects are acknowledged, especially K. Sharma, E. Morlec, G. Giovannini, B. M. Quandt, A. Pfammatter and L. Bernhard.

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